

PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF DETENTION CENTERS ON CHILDREN

by

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Abstract

Having little social media coverage, the issue of the separation of immigrant families in detention centers persists. The aim of this thesis paper is to generate a thorough analysis of the psychological effects children experience during their detention in immigration centers. The systematic review also addresses the inhuman living conditions and abuse immigrants endure while in detention. The study will also reveal the various subsequent types of mental illness children develop after being detained while looking at common disorders and establishing trending patterns. It will also analyze the 2018 zero-tolerance immigration policy that makes children subject to forced separation from families and explain its psychological impact (Wood, 2018). Qualitative methods, systematic reviews, and case studies were utilized to gather further analysis of the severe disorders children process after being held in detention centers and are analyzed throughout the paper.

Psychological Effects of Detention Centers on Children

Media outlets have exposed the cruelties and inhuman treatment that happens in Detention Centers. Stories and footage have been revealed that showcase the physical and verbal abuse they inflict on immigrants. Both children and adults are held in these institutes, so what kind of treatment do the children face? Unfortunately, they suffer the same fate as adults and experience psychological trauma in these centers. Immigration Centers were supposed to be a “refuge” for those who await to be returned to their origin country or await legal documents such as visas. These “refugees” refer to those detained and are diverse people with various legal statuses (Turnbull, 2017).

The severity of violence surrounding immigrant treatment in detention centers is a direct cause of the U.S. immigration system's flaws. This structural discrimination needs to be exposed in order to reform it. The lack of media coverage shows the underrepresentation of violence immigrants experience in these centers and undermines the severity of the social issue. The problem is: Children of fleeing immigrant families have experienced trauma due to the Immigration zero-tolerance policy (2018), which may lead to a lifetime of difficulties that can include negative psychological effects.

Historically, the United States and immigration have been controversial topics. Most of the country's solutions to the immigration problem have included a violent past. Unfortunately, the abuse of power continues to occur since the police enforcement in the immigration centers inflicts physical and mental harm on children and adults held in captivity. In 2018, the US government introduced a new law as a legal immigration control “strategy,” resulting in the detention of adults awaiting federal prosecution for illegal entry (Wood, 2018). Under the policy, every migrant, including asylum seekers, who attempted to cross the U.S. border anywhere other

than the official port of entry was to be detained and processed criminally (Refugees International, 2019). This law also had a subsequent effect on the removal of children to be separated across shelters in the US; the detention of children is known to be practiced in over one hundred countries worldwide (Wood, 2018).

In other words, the zero-tolerance policy forces separation between families, which causes trauma for both children and parents. Studies show that the cruel treatment children receive in detention centers leads to their development of mental illness, including anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and many others (MacLean et al., 2019). Hence, this literature review will focus on discussing the psychological effects children experience being held in these immigration centers through an analysis of qualitative studies. A discussion of the Immigration Zero-Tolerance policy and these children's trending psychological disorder patterns will be analyzed to examine the role that detention centers play in causing severe mental health trauma.

Refugee “Purpose”

Performing qualitative research, Newman et al. conducted research that explains the situation and general background information of why children and families are placed in “refuge.” Due to political and global unrest, many countries are reluctant to provide proper protection for individuals seeking asylum. They resort to a measure of so-called “humane deterrence,” which is known as Immigration Detention Centers (Newman, 2008). Due to the lack of concern for immigrant refugees, countries have developed several policies that limit or exclude them from civil entitlements at the national level. These include health care, housing, and work rights. In addition, there is also a severe lack of focus on high levels of trauma

exposure. Asylum seekers, including children, experience organized violence, sexual assault, and the death of inmates or family members (Newman, 2008). Hence, this article highlights the horrors children have to witness when they are held in these refugee camps.

Due to the lack of support from countries and their concerns, many families suffer many tragedies. Based on the events they witness in detainment, adolescents and adults develop psychological problems after release. The study reveals that half of the asylum seekers are children, whether accompanied by a parent or not. These children have been tortured and traumatized, having witnessed murder and cruelty, or have seen family members disappear (Newman, 2008). Not only that, but they have experienced the loss of shelter and suffered through the effects of diseases, malnutrition, and neglect. Thus, children are bound to retain psychological disorders after experiencing such horrific environments at a young age.

Conditions of Refugees

Nearly 22.8 million people are non-citizens in the US, and nearly 260,000 have sought some form of asylum or protection in the US since 2017 (Saadi, 2020). However, in their pursuit of help, immigrant populations experience inhuman treatment and unique health risks. Some of these risks include pre-migratory trauma, unsafe migration experiences, and post-migration discrimination (Saadi, 2020). Since lots of different risks are involved during the immigration process, immigrants have some health risks. Human rights abuses can occur across the spectrum of immigration since the population is often disregarded with proper treatment. After experiencing some of the conditions of immigration, the refugees may develop fears of deportation or mistrust of health care services and dissuading care-seeking behavior (Saadi, 2020). Some health consequences due to increased immigration enforcement and the fear of

deportation include cardiovascular risk factors, lower birth weights, and poor mental health (Saadi, 2020). These health behaviors are known to ripple throughout the immigrant communities as they all share similar experiences.

The conditions of these detentions have often been compared closely similar to those of prisons or jails. Detained individuals are held in secured facilities, are subject to strict control, and wear prison uniforms (Saadi, 2020). By mimicking a natural prison setting, immigrants in these centers inflict neglect, abuse, and challenges to economic stability (Saadi, 2020). These detention centers are not legally jails since the people are not charged with crimes, so why do they share similar experiences as prisoners? The biggest issue with detention centers is that they overlook violations of human rights they conduct. Reports of abuse and sexual assault are always ignored, despite having large numbers of complaints. However, rape and sexual assault are often underreported in immigration detention due to fears of social isolation and language barriers, but mostly due to the knowledge that allegations are not seriously investigated (Saadi, 2020). In other words, detention centers can cause abuse to immigrants without much consequence, which creates fear in those detained. Many of these facilities also place victims or mentally ill individuals into solitary confinement as punishment, despite its impact on physical and psychological well-being (Saadi, 2020).

The medical conditions of refugees are very limited, resulting in little to no care at all. Medical staff in detention centers are frequently understaffed or are focused on managing severe needs rather than chronic medical conditions (Saddi,2020). In other words, individuals in these detention centers are denied proper medical care due to the severe lack of resources available. As a result, this medical neglect reflects delayed diagnoses and care, followed by negative consequences for trauma-exposed individuals (Saadi, 2020).

Overcrowding has also become a problem as more adults and children are detained, causing more health risks. According to epidemiologic investigations conducted by local and state health departments, they have determined that several cases of mumps, measles, pneumonia, and other respiratory diseases have been documented to be in several detentions. Some other harsh conditions include sleep deprivation, dirty clothing, lack of privacy, and sanitation deficiencies (Saadi, 2020). Having multiple sanitation and health problems in the immigration centers puts children and parents in dangerous situations that they shouldn't be in.

Their inhumane and unsanitary treatment, yet it still has received no reformation. Statistics show that about 61.8% reported issues with food and water, 34.% with hygiene, and 45.6% with overcrowding, confinement, and the temperature being too cold (Saadi, 2020). The survey data inquired indicated that there are many problems with the conditions in the immigration centers, and individuals are growing more concerned about how they are being mistreated, but no action is taken to help them. Immigration centers have proved they cannot provide good living conditions for immigrants, yet overcrowding continues to develop.

After Detention

What exactly happens to children after being released from the immigration centers? In a 2018 systematic review, Robjant et al., analyzed and discussed the impacts and effects of detainment at an immigration center on children's mental health. The authors conducted a systematic search through databases and a supplementary manual search of references (Robjant, 2018). Ten studies included qualitative measures of mental health for children, adolescents, and adults who were or had previously been detained in Australia, the United Kingdom, or the United States of America (USA). In addition, study findings were compared with those of

participants who were non-detained refugees and migrants and from the same ethnic background (Robjant, 2018). The detained children had higher rates of mental health difficulties than the general population.

The longer a refugee stays in detention centers, the higher the risk of developing a psychiatric disorder (Robjant, 2018). Individuals reported increased anxiety, depression, somatoform disorders [physical sensations and bodily pain caused by mental illness], and PTSD symptoms. These findings demonstrate that post-migratory stressors negatively affect these individuals, who are already vulnerable to mental health difficulties due to their exposure to traumatic events in asylums. Those detained in the host country experience more stressors, reflecting the detention centers' hostile environment on the refugees' mental health. They are also denied their liberty, left with uncertainty regarding return to their country of origin, social isolation, abuse from staff, riots, forceful removal, hunger strikes, and self-harm (Robjant, 2018).

Several clinicians have expressed their concerns that these immigration centers increase mental health difficulties in adults and children and have called for an end to such practices (Robjant, 2018). Overall, this article discussed the severity of the mental health status of asylum seekers and demonstrated the extent to which their trauma runs. The study's limitation lies in targeting only one specific group (which was anonymous) and increasing the validity of results for that ethnic group, limiting the generalizability of other groups. However, despite this limitation, the study consistently provides data that shows the results of the poor mental health of detained individuals in these centers (Robjant, 2019).

Methodology

Literature Research

This paper's literature review was generated using sites such as JSTOR, PsychINFO, Google Scholar, and Science Direct. The keywords used to find case studies relating to the thesis consisted of IMMIGRATION (refugee* asylum*), MENTAL HEALTH (psychological effects* depression* PTSD*), POLICY (zero-tolerance policy* immigration laws*, and REFORMATION (reform* immigration treatment* living conditions*). The articles utilized were from 2008 to 2022 and were peer-reviewed articles or sources from educational sites. The articles that the database was looked over and those that contain information on immigration and mental health, living and treatment conditions of immigrants, zero-tolerance policy, and reformation were compiled into the literature review.

Study Inclusion

The methodology consisted of a mixed-methods approach since both are crucial in addressing the research question. Using qualitative methods, systematic reviews were used to provide the background context and investigate policies that correlated with the issue of immigration. On the other hand, a quantitative method was utilized to discuss the statistical findings from previous case studies that examined issues similar to the psychological effects children experienced in immigration centers. Having a mixed-methods approach provided further analysis of the severe disorders children process after being held in detention centers. Based on the secondary research conducted, Robjant (2009), Von Werthern (2018), Wood LCN (2018), Feliciano & Green (2022), Freedom for Immigrants (2018), Mcleod (2018), O'Leary (2019), Peterson (2018), Refugees International (2019), Saadi et al. (2020), and Willis (2019) conducted qualitative research and

provided an in-depth analysis of the research focus. For quantitative research, MacLean (2018; 2019) and Newman (2008) were able to provide case studies where data were analyzed to justify their theories. In total, fourteen case studies or systematic reviews were used and were limited to English peer-reviewed articles. Some of the developmental questions that will be discussed are: *What negative psychological effects do children under 18 years old suffer when held in detention centers? What specific mental health issues do children (under 18 years old) encounter when they are released from immigration centers? What negative psychological effects do families face when they are released from detention centers?*

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1yEG20liCweYClZ1doYywpQCuzL6taTzSHklAKwVdsNA/edit?usp=sharing>

Participants

Since multiple studies were gathered, various participants were used to represent the research. Participants included both females and males, primarily Hispanic, and had prior experience being held in detention centers. Both children around the ages of 4 to 17 and adults eighteen years or older were taken into account.

Results

Trending Patterns

Based on the analytical research conducted, trending patterns of the common psychological effects, such as depression, anxiety, and PTSD, were found across all case studies. Once the trend was identified, a deeper dive into common psychological effects were determined and discussed. Along the way, the zero-tolerance immigration policy was discovered and examined to explain how it contributed to the distress of immigrant children and families. The research also

allowed the examination of type III trauma. This type of trauma occurs when an individual experiences a series of violent and persuasive events at an early age that continue over time and was found to be linked to the psychological effects the immigrant children suffered after detention. This paper was based on secondary research, so finding various case studies was crucial in order to discover trending patterns and generate a detailed analysis of the problem the paper dives into.

Interviews

As previously mentioned, the conditions of immigration centers are horrific. This can be further described through a series of interviews to formulate a clear picture of the hardships immigrants had to endure in these facilities. In 2019, O’Leary interviewed Elora Mukherjee, who was a director of the Columbian’s Immigrants Rights Clinic. She had interviewed multiple migrant children and families in Texas and in Florida facilities and witnessed firsthand the conditions these individuals find themselves in. O’Leary asked Mukherjee to talk about her involvement and what she saw during her visit to the centers. Mukherjee was appalled by the conditions, and never in her twelve years in her line of work had she seen such “degradation” and “inhumanity” (O’Leary, 2019). She described the scenery by saying that the children were dirty, scared, and hungry. For example, the children were still wearing the same clothes they had worn crossing the border and were covered in bodily fluids, including urine and breast milk for the breastfeeding moms (O’Leary, 2019).

Not only have the children and families not been given the opportunity to shower, but every child spoken to was incredibly hungry (O’Leary, 2019). The same amount of food portion was given to adults and children. This proved to be problematic as mothers had higher caloric

needs compared to smaller children (O’Lear, 2019). Unfortunately, the same food is served daily, and children do not receive any beneficial food such as fruits, vegetables, or milk (O’Lear, 2019). O’Leary asked Mukherjee to compare these conditions to what she saw in previous administrations. Mukherjee replied she had never seen such “degrading” treatment toward children (O’Lear, 2019). Those aged 7-9 years old are ordered to care for the younger children, about two to three years old. This proves to be problematic as the “older” children do not know how to properly take care of the young.

The 2020 pandemic was a worldwide spread of a virus called COVID-19 that caused panic to many as its effects were unknown. How did the news of this virus impact detention centers, and what occurred during the initial stages of the pandemic in these facilities? Some answers can be found in the documentary entitled “The Facility,” which showed the chronicle of experiences migrants faced at the Irwin County Detention Center during the COVID-19 pandemic (Feliciano & Green, 2022). Ivette Feliciano interviewed the documentor, Seth Wessler, about the responses he saw when the virus first began. In 2020, about “38,000” migrants held in detention centers had their court dates canceled and were left with no information on how long they would be waiting (Feliciano & Green, 2022). Legally, the U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement (ICE) cannot detain people with pending cases, but many choose to stay due to the threat of the pandemic (Feliciano & Green, 2022). The migrants were described as under significant stress as they saw how fast the pandemic was moving and worried that everyone would be at risk when the virus infiltrated the detention center (Feliciano & Green, 2022). Wessler says that no information about what the virus was provided to the detainees, and no form of protection was offered. No masks were given to them, social distancing was not enforced (standing six feet apart from each other], and guards did not mask (Feliciano & Green, 2022).

The Irwin County facility held, on average, about 754 immigrants in 2020, of which 146 of those individuals tested positive for COVID-19 in February of that year. It is implied that many more positive cases could have gone undetected as the center lacked routine testing and proper facility reporting of positive cases (Feliciano & Green, 2022). In response to the lack of information and proper care, immigrants had a hunger strike and demanded there be mask requirements and the halt of bringing in new detainees (Feliciano & Green, 2022). The facility's staff responded with physical abuse and solitary confinement in response to the protests.

The documentary by Wessler was meant to show that once the pandemic made its way to the detention center, no proper measures were taken to reduce the spread of the COVID-19 virus in the facility. The lack of resources offered to the detainees is a pattern of deprivation of human rights. Even before the pandemic, the immigrants in these detentions lacked the proper sources for basic hygiene, and most found themselves hungry. In other words, the documentary provided a glimpse into the cruel conditions immigrants found themselves in at the beginning of the pandemic and showcased the lack of protection and information they received.

Common Disorders

The after-effects children experience after being held in detention centers vary widely, but all present similar mental health problems. In a 2019 study, researchers used the Parent-Report Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) to interview 425 mothers about their eldest child (ages 4-17) for a brief behavioral screening to assess pro-social behavior, emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity, and peer problems (MacLean et al., 2019). About 150 children aged 9 and above completed the UCLA Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder Reaction Index (PTSD-RI). The results of this case study revealed elevated peer

problems (14%), emotional problems (32%), and total mental health difficulties (10%) on the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ; MacLean et al., 2019). On the other hand, younger children (ages 4–8 years) showed more difficulties with conduct, hyperactivity, and total mental health problems.

The central idea of this narrative focuses on a study conducted to evaluate the psychological status of children after being in a traumatic environment. The study by MacLean et al. (2019) found that children and adults placed in these immigration centers demonstrated high rates of mental health problems such as depression and anxiety. Additionally, children that were separated from their mothers showed even greater mental health issues than those who remained with their families at the centers (MacLean et al., 2019). Some studies conducted outside the U.S. demonstrated that detained immigrant children have a high prevalence of depression (10%), anxiety (10%), and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD, 20%) (MacLean et al., 2019). The study demonstrates the extent of the trauma for these children who had to endure a harsh environment in the immigration centers. Children experienced significant emotional and psychological trauma due to maltreatment at these facilities. The strength of the MacLean study is the inclusion of a wide range of participant candidates and a focus on the mental health consequences children face after leaving the centers.

Trending Patterns

Many mental disorders are commonly developed by detainee children and share similar patterns. In a similar 2018 study, Von Werthern et al. provided similar findings as in the MacLean study. Using a systematic review methodology, three databases were used to find qualitative case studies, surveyed detained immigrants, and reported on mental health problems.

All analyzed case studies were published in peer-reviewed journals. The review found that children, adolescents, and adults experienced elevated levels of mental health problems since the trauma the children faced in custody severely impacted them negatively. Based on the review, a wide range of psychological disturbances was found since all children had at least one psychiatric disorder.

The most frequent conditions present were depression, anxiety, PTSD, and somatization. The majority of the children also reported having trouble sleeping (65-100%), eating problems (100%), self-harm (25-80%), and suicidal ideation (50%), emphasizing the severity of the effects children experience once they manage to leave the detention centers (Werthern, 2018). These assessments were conducted following the release of the “immigration” centers and also found that 57% of adolescents within the same detention facility continued to meet a diagnosis of PTSD (Werthern, 2018). According to psychiatric interviews, children were ten times more likely to develop these disorders following their detention (Werthern, 2018). Thus, demonstrating that there is a trending pattern of children developing various mental disorders after recovering from their treatment in refugee camps.

In addition, children of all ages displayed common emotional and behavioral problems. Young children (ages 3-6) showed a developmental delay that included frequent crying, disturbed sleep routines, language delays, loss of previously acquired cognitive skills, and a return to naps (Werthern, 2018). Amongst older children (aged 7–11), there was high depression, anxiety, and PTSD (Werthern, 2018). This assessment shows that young and older children experience some sort of psychological trauma after leaving detention centers. This systematic review provides a good analysis of cumulative studies that share similar results for children experiencing psychological distress due to detention. However, one of its limitations is a lack of

random sampling. This limitation denies the representation of other cultural populations, so more diverse data is needed to generalize the detainee population as a whole. However, the review's strength lies in the multiple case studies it provides to conduct a strong analysis of the data collected.

Type III Trauma

In order to see the differences between normal and immigrant child development, an examination of Erikson's theory is discussed. Normal development comes in a series of stages which can be referenced by Erikson's Stages of Psychosocial Development. In this theory, normal development happens in eight stages. In the Trust vs. Mistrust stage [0-1 ½ yrs old] the infant is uncertain about the world and relies on a caregiver for stability and care. If the infant receives consistent care, they will most likely develop a sense of trust which will be carried through other relationships. If no care is provided, mistrust, suspicion, and anxiety can develop, and the infant will not have confidence in the world around them (McLeod, 2018).

The Autonomy vs. Shame stage [1 ½ -3 yrs old] is when children become focused on developing a sense of personal control over physical skills and a sense of independence. Success in this stage leads to the virtue of will and will feel confident in their own ability to survive in the world. Failure in this stage by being overly controlled or criticized results in becoming overly dependent upon others, lack of self-esteem, and feeling a sense of shame or doubt in their abilities (McLeod, 2018).

In the Initiative vs. Guilt stage [3-5 yrs old], children assert themselves more frequently through directing play and other social interactions. During this time, children start to plan activities and initiate them. As a result, children develop a sense of initiative and feel confident

in their ability to lead others and make decisions. Failure in this stage results of growing feelings of guilt which can impact their ability to interact with others and their creativity (McLeod, 2018).

During the Industry vs. Inferiority stage [5-12 yrs old], children are encouraged and reinforced for their initiative. They begin to feel competent and confident in their ability to achieve goals. If not encouraged, the child begins to feel inferior while doubting their abilities (McLeod, 2018).

In the Identity vs Role Confusion stage [12-18 yrs old], adolescents search for a sense of personal identity through an exploration of personal values, beliefs, and goals. This stage is critically important as this is where the child has to learn the roles they will occupy as an adult. The adolescent will re-examine their identity and try to find out exactly who he or she is. Failure to find an answer to self results in role confusion or an identity crisis (McLeod, 2018).

Erikson's theory of development showcases what normal development should look like but also gives a glimpse of what it means to fail the milestones necessary for an individual to have a "normal" experience. However, living in a detention center develops distress in children's mental health, and type III trauma can be developed. Wood and other authors conducted qualitative research to discuss their concerns for children's level of trauma and mental health needs before U.S. entry since hardships await them in detention centers. Having children separated from their caregivers and detained for an unknown amount of time facilitates a stress response that can develop toxic stress, known as type III trauma (Wood LC, 2018).

This type of trauma occurs when an individual experiences a series of violent and persuasive events at an early age that continue over time throughout development. The chronic pounding of stress hormones in children's bodies risks becoming toxic (Wood LC, 2018). In other words, stress hormones can activate immune changes and the development of diseases and

disorders. A child with high adversity triples the lifetime risk of developing lung cancer, heart disease, and many more (Wood LC, 2018). With this in mind, children in immigration centers experience major psychological trauma that can further develop into physical altercations. The harsh environments children experience in detention centers are demonstrated by the high levels of stress they have to endure with the physical and verbal abuse they are inflicted with.

In response, children can develop complex patterns of protective responses, which include hyperarousal [an abnormal state of increased responsiveness to stimuli], hypervigilance, agitation, or hyperarousal [a person's exposure to painful emotions or lower levels of sensory deprivation than they can bare] (Wood LC, 2018). In other words, since children are exposed to different harsh environments in the centers, children are at risk of developing type III trauma since they are being exposed to severe violence. Thus, this systematic review explains that children separated by force tend to experience psychological and physical trauma to the body. This research uniqueness derives from the discussion of type three trauma and its effects on children forced to be separated from their mothers.

In general, exposure to trauma can influence children to develop some coping mechanisms. For example, they can become overly sensitive to the moods of others, they can withhold their own emotions from others, and never let others see when they feel angry or sad (Peterson, 2018). Complex trauma can affect children in many different ways. When caregivers exploit or abuse children, the child learns that the world is a terrible place and has difficulty developing strong attachments to a caregiver in the future (Peterson, 2018). Those children that do not have a healthy relationship with caregivers have been seen to be more vulnerable to stress, expressing their emotions, and could react violently to situations (Peterson, 2018). A complex

trauma history can cause the child to have problems in romantic relationships, friendships, and with authority figures like teachers or police officers.

Trauma can also impact a child's thinking and learning. In other words, they may struggle with sustaining attention or curiosity due to trauma reminders. They may also show deficits in language development and abstract reasoning skills, which would require support in the academic environment (Peterson, 2018). Dissociation is also often seen in children with complex trauma histories. When children encounter overwhelming, terrifying experiences, there is a possibility they may dissociate or mentally separate themselves from the experience (Peterson, 2018). In other words, the child may perceive themselves as detached from their bodies and may feel as if they are in a dream. Dissociation can affect a child's ability to be fully present in activities of daily life, which can significantly fracture a child's sense of time and continuity (Peterson, 2018). As a result, it can have adverse effects on learning, classroom behavior, and social interactions (Peterson, 2018).

Physically when a child grows up in a constantly stressful environment, their immune system and body's stress response systems may not develop normally (Peterson, 2018). In adulthood, these systems may automatically respond as if the person was under extreme stress. This can be seen through physiological reactivity, such as rapid heart pounding or breathing during stressful situations (Peterson, 2018). Stress can also impair the development of the brain and nervous system. An absence of mental stimulation in neglectful environments can limit the development of the brain to its full potential (Peterson, 2018). Children with trauma histories can develop chronic or physical complaints, like headaches or stomach aches. As adults, they have been shown to have these chronic conditions and may engage in "risky" behaviors such as smoking, substance use, and diet habits that lead to obesity (Peterson, 2018). In other words, the

general consequences of “normal” children experiencing trauma also correlate with the trauma children face in immigration centers since they develop similar coping mechanisms and experience a form of type III trauma.

Immigration policy/ Separation Effects

There are many legal aspects that play a role in immigration. However, the Immigration zero-tolerance policy [a policy that allows forced separation of families] seems to be the most common psychological cause of additional distress to children and families. In a recent study, MacLean et al. (2020) performed research that focused on the zero-tolerance policy, which allowed immediate separation of parents traveling with children. The methodology consisted of a cross-sectional evaluation of 73 children held at an immigration center who had been reunited with their mothers after experiencing forced separation (MacLean et al., 2020). The criteria chosen to be part of the study included mothers who had at least one child between ages 4 and 17 years detained with them and spoke fluent English or Spanish and had them complete the Parent-Report version of the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ; MacLean et al., 2020). Having to separate from family units causes several children extreme psychological difficulties. Even after the family members reunited, they still had to recover from the impact that the separation caused.

The main concern with the zero-tolerance policy is the mental health impact caused by forced separation. The study found that children who experienced forced separation had higher rates of abnormal emotional and peer problems compared to other samples acquired (MacLean, 2020). Thus, demonstrating that additional trauma is inflicted when children must experience the horrors of the detention centers alone. Witnessing such events at a young age causes emotional

harm and creates higher risks of mental health problems. These risks include developing depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and anxiety disorders (MacLean, 2020). This study's limitation is based on the sample size since the mothers were recruited from the visitation centers. However, this study was unique since no data had been collected about the distress children face after being forcefully separated from their mothers. The findings from this study are very important and will help many others that look to discuss forced separation and its effects.

Discussion

This systematic review sought to find trending patterns of psychological effects children endure in immigration centers and look for reformation solutions. Many people who seek refuge are met with harsh treatment in immigration centers. The place that is supposed to be safe to await travel to their origin country is a place where they are abused and forced to experience trauma. Children are no exception and develop many psychological problems due to the experience. Being placed in environments like this subjects children to trauma which develops into anxiety, PTSD, depression, and many other mental disorders, as many researchers have found. However, more research and awareness of this problem need to be spread through the media to stop the maltreatment of innocent children. A primary recommendation for change would be the reformation of the living conditions and treatment immigrants face in the program.

Reformation

Medical Reformation

Sanitation should be the top priority in reforming detention centers, and the problem of overcrowding needs to be addressed and minimized. In order to do this, legal and social efforts [such as program organizations, "volunteers," or legal team support] need to be discussed and

properly executed. Legal and human rights groups are the key to providing individual support to those detained and monitoring the conditions of the detentions. Healthcare workers should also team up with legal experts who understand the detention system in order to reform the problems and living conditions immigrants face in detention centers. Due to the anti-immigrant political climate, monitoring needs to be held over detention centers until better-structured oversight is conducted at the federal level (Saadi, 2020). In other words, to start reforming the environment in the refugee camps, medical and legal experts need to work together to improve the living conditions of immigrants and promote better basic human rights when they are in these facilities.

Unfortunately, many immigration detention centers do not provide the proper resources to detain so many. Medical neglect in these situations has proven to contribute to many immigration deaths in the centers (Freedom for Immigrants, 2018). A medical report conducted in 2017 demonstrated the systematic failures of the immigration camps by the unreasonable delays in receiving medical care and the amount of unqualified medical staff hired (Freedom for Immigrants, 2018). The report also mentions that substandard care [arises when a doctor or other medical professional fails to adhere to the appropriate standard of care when treating a patient] was evident in 16 out of 18 deaths (Freedom for Immigrants, 2018). Some examples of substandard care included: failure to follow up on symptoms that required attention, lack of mental health care [especially the misuse of solitary confinement for people with mental health conditions], and some medical personnel practicing beyond their expertise (Freedom for Immigrants, 2018).

To put the detainee's medical environment in perspective, we will examine the 2011 case of Raul Morales. Regrettably, he died after a delayed surgery to remove an abdominal mass (Freedom for Immigrants, 2018). However, experts determined that he had presented symptoms

of cancer as far as two years before he died. His health concerns were not attended to until one month before he passed away (Freedom for Immigrants, 2018). Morales' case demonstrates the lack of medical attention detainees receive and how they lack the proper care in these facilities. If the medical resources in detention centers were reliable, Morales would have realized he suffered from cancer two years before he died.

Detained individuals also have limited rights and are at risk of retaliation if they decide to engage in activism. That is why in order to improve the conditions in detention centers, it is crucial that healthcare professionals enforce human rights. They need to address new strategies to address the social-structural determinants of health in order to promote better health conditions for immigrants (Saadi, 2020). If more medical staff and resources are provided to the detention facilities, more attentive care can be given to sick or injured detainees. However, in order for this to happen, funding or donations needs to be provided in order to supply several detentions with medical supplies in order to treat patients in the detentions. In addition, medical volunteer programs can be created with the goal of accumulating basic hygiene products, medical equipment, or any additional support the detainees may need in regard to their health.

Legal Reformation

Another area for reform would involve the legal aspect of the situation. In 2019, a \$4.6 billion border aid bill was passed by Congress (Willis, 2019). Before the bill passed there were two drafts proposed by the Senate and the House of Representatives. The Senate version was chosen and signed by the President of the United States at the time. The bill included aid in alleviating conditions for detained migrant children by sending \$2.9 billion to restore the

resources of the Department of Health and Human Services (Willis, 2019). The remaining \$1.3 billion would go to the Department of Homeland Security for Border Patrol to improve the conditions in the detention centers (Willis, 2019). The fund would help provide better essential items such as clothing, hygiene products, and baby formula (Willis, 2019). This bill is an example of legal reform that needs to be implemented in order to improve immigrants living conditions in the facilities. By taking legal action, funds can be provided for more resources. In the Mukherjee interview mentioned earlier, he proposed a legal call to action. Immediate congressional hearings on the horrific conditions at the border need to be issued and everyone (regardless of political background) needs to reach out to Congress (O’Lear, 2019). Demands need to be made to investigate the living conditions in which children and adults are detained. He argues that “this is not how we should treat people,” especially children in America. Further, the author suggests that society needs to be more invested in situations occurring around show concern by demanding investigations to be opened regardless of the activities occurring in the detention facilities.

Strengths and Limitations

A thorough research strategy was implemented in order to collect several forms of data to portray the situation the children and immigrants face in detention centers. The data extraction was done in consideration and was applied in a systematic approach to combining several literature on the mental health effects children experience during and after detention. All articles utilized were peer-reviewed or extracted from educational sources. Finally, since the systematic review used secondary research, some limitations occurred. The sources were not primary, so for future research, primary interviews could be more strengthening to the topic. More questions could be asked regarding the impact of detention and their mental health state after being

released. The review also generalized participants, so having a solid ethnicity group or age range could better specify the immigration groups.

What this review adds to existing reviews

This review supports similar findings other researchers have discovered regarding the mental health impact on immigrant children and families. The review also explained the generalized situation of the Immigration Refugee Program and provided insight on the living conditions and treatment the refugees faced. Not only that, but the review touched on the zero tolerance policy, which allowed the separation of families and resulted in stress for children. Type III trauma has rarely been discussed, so this review connected this topic with mental health struggles.

Conclusion

This systematic review is the first one of our knowledge to contain immigrant reformation solutions to better the living conditions of refugee seekers in asylums. However, this review is not the first to examine the mental health issues children experience after being held in detention, as primary research and case studies exist to analyze that data. Future research may need to be conducted to provide more reformation resolutions in the medical and legal fields to improve refugees' living conditions and legal systems.

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